

Making the Global Open Research Commons Truly Global

**Report from the
Lorentz Workshop,
held July 21 - 25, 2025**

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Executive summary

Models are frameworks to reflect about complex phenomena. This holds for all models, be it mathematical models or reference models for communication. To keep research open and to harvest from the autonomous, unchained innovativeness of research production is a timely challenge. To find a shared language is a precondition to do so. This Lorentz workshop gave information professionals from a wide variety of settings the ability to reflect thoroughly, to improve and to test a model which has been co-designed by many stakeholders over the last seven years to provide a common language and facilitate international interoperability.

This workshop was held July 21-25, 2025, and organised by a subset of the chairs of the [Research Data Alliance](#) (RDA) Global Open Research Commons (GORC) [Interest Group](#) and [International Implementations Working Group](#), augmented and reinforced by staff from [SURE](#). It was held as a [Lorentz Centre](#) workshop, embracing the advantages of this specific location for an in-depth and broad ranging collaborative exploration of a range of issues. The specific setting of a Lorentz Workshop gave space and time to re-inspect past debates, and to share experiences to implement the model in practice. The workshop discussed a wide range of issues, which are documented in this report and its appendices.

The overwhelming message from those who attended the workshop is that the GORC International Model is well-constructed, useful and being used. The structure of the model draws on existing good practice as well as fundamental information science principles, and has been carefully refined through community review. The model is applicable to a wide range of settings. While it might need further fine-tuning as with any model, it is already an excellent epistemic framework to enable individuals

and organisations to reflect theoretically and practically about their activities and needs in the realm of digital research infrastructure. And, the model is being used in practice for a variety of purposes, including interoperability between commons and internally within organisations. It is already having an impact by shaping national and pan-national digital research infrastructures. Examples presented at the workshop included:

1. [EGI](#) is using the model to think about its role in the context of the [European Open Science Cloud](#) (EOSC) Federation and to consider GORC governance and sustainability examples and best practices that are suitable for multi-supply federated environments.
2. [SURF](#) is using the model as a reference model for engagement, planning and alignment when considering the services they provide and how these would appear as part of the Netherland's Large Scale Research Infrastructures (LSRI) and an EOSC National Node.
3. [CSC](#) (Finland) and SURF (Netherlands) are adapting and utilising the GORC International Model in the context of developing national nodes for EOSC.
4. The GORC International Model is a source of repository attributes for use in the RDA [Community-based catalogue of requirements for trustworthy Technical Repository Service Providers Working Group](#) (TRSPs) WG
5. GORC is an organising Ontology for the [RDA Knowledge Base](#) (in development)

A number of benefits from using the GORC International Model were identified across multiple use-cases:

1. To serve as a common vocabulary, such as for EOSC, and for disparate organisations at national scale.
2. To serve as a blueprint for data sharing and governance related to it.
3. To provide a broader context for a specific objective - for example, sharing data requires additional provisions - authorization and authentication infrastructure (AAI), monitoring, sustainability, etc.
4. To be potentially usable for commercial infrastructure providers - possibly with the exception of governance-related elements, and by generalising the current focus on research.
5. To be used by organisations to develop their own internal maturity models and measure progress, as well as set up their own benchmarking by describing what they do, how they do it and how it might be improved.

The workshop also generated a range of new insights that would not have been possible without the multiplier-value of the Lorentz Centre setting and the wide range of stakeholders who contributed their time and energy to the discussions. These should not be seen as negatives, but as a validation of the value of the model to date, and an investment in its ongoing success:

The focus of the GORC International Model initiative needs to move from development/refinement of the model to adoption/use of the model;

Changes to the GORC International Model should only be introduced based on feedback from adoption/use and in a staged and controlled fashion; and Long term sustainability and governance of the GORC International Model initiative and outputs needs closer attention.

1. Introduction

1.1 GORC Context

This workshop was organised by a subset of the chairs of the [Research Data Alliance](#) Global Open Research Commons (GORC) [Interest Group](#) and [International Implementations Working Group](#), augmented and reinforced by staff from [SURF](#). It was held as a [Lorentz Centre](#) workshop, embracing the advantages of this specific location for an in-depth and broad ranging collaborative exploration of a range of issues.

Looking at the history of how this workshop came about, the GORC Interest Group (GORC-IG) grew out of a Birds of a Feather meeting held as part of the 11th Research Data Alliance Plenary in Berlin in March 2018. The goal of the IG, formally established in October 2019, was to provide a neutral forum to coordinate the development of a typology to describe what are referred to as 'Open Science Commons' or 'Data commons' within the research commons umbrella as a first step in a roadmap towards international interoperability¹. The RDA Interest Groups work as bottom-up networks addressing specific areas of interest.

The topic of this specific IG emerged as a consequence of the ongoing interwovenness of knowledge production in and outside of academia. In its work as a first step, the GORC-IG examined a range of existing research commons architectures to review current practice. As a subsequent step, the GORC-IG generated a definition of a global research commons: a global trusted ecosystem that provides seamless access to high-quality interoperable research outputs and services. Last, it developed a typology of the Essential Elements in a global research commons and a set of definitions for each of the essential elements².

The GORC International Model (IM) Working Group (WG) was established in 2021 to focus on what a research commons should consider to position towards international interoperability. The GORC IM WG drew on the essential elements identified by the GORC-IG and consolidated a large range of resources and expert feedback to generate the International Model.³ The GORC International Model consists of a number of elements (with associated categories, subcategories, attributes and features) to be considered when undertaking the development of a commons of any kind, at any stage. It creates a well-defined terminology, while at the same time trying to stay agnostic and flexible to be applied to various practice settings. Although the categories, subcategories, attributes and features are marked as either core, desirable or optional, the model does not mandate what should be implemented, or in what way; the decisions on what is relevant, and where resources should be invested, will vary depending on the environment and priorities of the implementer.

1. Treloar, A. and Woodford, C.J. (2024). Global Open Research Commons: Creating an International Model for Improved Interoperability and Collaboration. *Data Science Journal*, 23: 56, pp. 1–9. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2024-056>

2. Jones, Sarah, Leggott, Mark, Lopez Albacete, Javier, Pascu, Corina, Payne, Karen, Schoupe, Michel, Treloar, Andrew, & Global Open Research Commons IG. (2023). GORC IG: Typology and Definitions (1.0). <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00087>

3. Payne, K., Corrie, B., Crawley, F., Harrower, N., Macneil, R., Maxwell, L., Sansone, S.-A., Treloar, A., Woodford, C., Åkerström, W. N., & RDA GORC International Model WG. (2023). The Global Open Research Commons International Model Report, Version 1. <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00097>; Woodford, C., Treloar, A., Leggott, M., Payne, K., Jones, S., Lopez Albacete, J., Madalli, D., Genova, F., Dharmawardena, K., Chibhira, N., Nyberg Åkerström, W., Macneil, R., Nurnberger, A., Pfeiffenberger, H., Tanifuji, M., Zhang, Q., Jones, N., Sesink, L., & Wood-Charlson, E. (2024). The Global Open Research Commons International Model, version 1.1 Model Overview. <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00119>

4. A **profile** is a specific, filled out profile template for an organisation at a particular time. A **profile template** is a refined subset of items in the model to better suit a subset of research commons. A completed profile will at minimum include a response to each item (category, subcategory, attribute, and feature) in the profile template regarding relevance, implementation status and intent, with evidence of its implementation if available.

5. **Adoption** here means the use, agreed upon by all relevant stakeholders, of any of the GORC outputs (e.g. typology, model as a whole or in part) at any granularity (e.g. project, unit, organization, federations). For example, if a project lead wishes to adopt the GORC typology (i.e. essential elements) in their project, the project team should agree and participate in that use. At the organizational level, adoption of the model may be the creation of an organizational profile that is endorsed by all senior leadership members.

Having said this, a model proves its usefulness only if applied in either a scientific discourse or as in case of the GORC International Model in the case of a concrete practice. The Lorentz workshop contributed to both directions of 'testing' the model.

The GORC IM WG concluded in 2024. Work on the GORC International Model's documentation and outputs supporting use continue in the GORC International Implementations WG (GORC II WG), which was established in early 2025.

1.2 Workshop context

The support from the Lorentz Centre enabled the coordinators to bring together a group of up to 25 people, and also provided use of a custom-built collaboration venue, payment for a workshop dinner, and access to discounted hotel rates. The Lorentz Centre has a well-deserved reputation which facilitates attracting high-quality attendees, whose organisations covered remaining travel costs. Its facilities are specifically designed to support intense, focussed, and in-depth conversations, which otherwise might not happen.

The workshop goals for participants were to gain a deeper understanding of the current GORC International Model and the purposes to which it can be put, to explore why international interoperability matters and mechanisms to achieve it, and to create a profile of their own organisation. Currently many organisations in the realm of research infrastructures are confronted, or tasked with proving that they operate under the paradigm of Open Science, and are challenged to further professionalise their network position and services. Here, the GORC International Model is specifically valuable as it enables the development of profiles⁴ as specific instantiations of the model for a particular organisation or scope set by a user, say for a collection of organisations or for a particular project within an organisation. Creating a profile is a key step towards framing one's organisation vis a vis the GORC International Model, and needs to be undertaken as part of the process of adopting⁵ the model.

The workshop goals for the coordinators were to test and improve the Essential Elements and the International Model with a carefully selected community from a range of disciplines, roles and countries. This included mapping out pairwise interoperability between elements, and identifying areas for updating, augmenting, and building the model. The coordinators also aimed to identify a range of uses and adoption tools for the model across communities and to isolate areas where the GORC International Model is over-complex, insufficiently detailed, or poorly explained.

Global open research commons

Essential elements

V1.3, GORC-IG, 2024

were available: a shared collaborative notes document (64 pages), a discussions summary (25 pages), and this report text, which was circulated to all participants for comment before finalisation. As a result of this ongoing report-back and structured feedback process, this report is based on the consensus position of the workshop attendees as a whole.

3. Workshop outcomes

The overwhelming message from those who attended the workshop is that the GORC International Model is well-constructed, useful and being used. The structure of the model draws on existing good practice as well as fundamental information science principles, and has been carefully refined through community review. The model is applicable to a wide range of settings. While it might need further fine-tuning as with any model, it is already an excellent epistemic framework to enable individuals and organisations to reflect theoretically and practically about their practices and needs in the realm of research infrastructure. And, the model is being used in practice for a variety of purposes, including interoperability between commons and internally within organisations. It is already having an impact by shaping national and pan-national digital research infrastructures.

A number of benefits from using the GORC International Model were identified across multiple use-cases:

1. To serve as a common vocabulary, such as for EOSC, and for disparate organisations at national scale.
2. To serve as a blueprint for data sharing and governance related to it.
3. To provide a broader context for a specific objective - for example, sharing data requires additional provisions - AAI, monitoring, sustainability, etc.
4. To be potentially usable for commercial infrastructure providers - possibly with the exception of governance-related elements, and by generalising the current focus on research.
5. To be used by organisations to develop their own internal maturity models and measure progress, as well as set up their own benchmarking by describing what they do, how they do it and how it might be improved.

The workshop also generated a range of new insights that would not have been possible without the multiplier-value of the Lorentz setting and the wide range of stakeholders who contributed their time and energy to the discussions. These should not be seen as negatives, but as a validation of the value of the model to date, and an investment in its ongoing success.

1. The focus of the GORC initiative needs to move from development/refinement of the model to adoption/use⁶ of the model

6. Use differs from adoption as it includes any use of any of the GORC outputs, with or without stakeholder buy-in, review, or acknowledgment. Adopters are users of the GORC outputs by definition.

7. Use cases are a description of the benefits, gains, implementations, and other relevant context for a particular use of the GORC International Model. Specific implementations of use cases, i.e. applied to a particular organization, are use case examples

8. Slices are thematic subsets of the GORC International Model that cut across essential elements, connecting items relevant to a particular role or topic such as academic librarians or FAIR.

2. Changes to the model should only be introduced based on feedback from adoption/use and in a staged and controlled fashion
3. Long term sustainability and governance of the GORC initiative and outputs needs closer attention

For adoption/use, this includes creation of narratives and documentation to clearly communicate the GORC mission and value to a variety of Digital Research Infrastructure (DRI) stakeholders, the creation of templates and use cases⁷ to encourage and facilitate adoption, and the development of profiles and examples showing how the model can be used for specific instances. The model must remain as agnostic and unambiguous as possible, and principles, implementation needs, legal requirements, and more can be applied or integrated into the model for a particular social, economic, cultural, and political context, and at varying levels of granularity. A GORC profile is a specific instantiation of the model for a specific organisation, illustrating their choices based on their context and their reason for undertaking the modelling. Other outcomes that would facilitate adoption, such as visualizations, interactive adoption and navigation tools, connections between the essential elements, and slices⁸ highlighting roles or stakeholder group interests would be an asset at this stage.

Multiple structural and content changes were recommended. Many of the minor recommendations were recorded as comments on the [live V1.1 of the model](#) and it was agreed that these should be tested against a large collection of real profiles, perhaps arranged through a registry with access to users. However, it was confirmed that no changes to the model should be made until a registry of users and profiles has been created, such that feedback on which changes would be helpful or harmful can be investigated with the intended audience.

Lastly, it was recognized that the GORC International Model's development has reached a stage where investing in formal governance frameworks would better support its continued adoption, evolution, and long-term sustainability. Such a governance structure would include but might be larger than RDA, and also add representation from institutional host(s) and dedicated organised support from adopters. The [GORC IG](#) co-chairs plan to investigate new governance models to better match the scope and needs of the GORC initiative.

Generally, it was well understood and emphasized that the [GORC typology](#) and [model](#) have already provided a common language that will facilitate the delivery of interoperability goals across the DRI ecosystem.

4. Main points discussed

4.1 Original intentions⁹

While the GORC International Model supports the development of individual commons, it also supports the work necessary to make the commons interoperable. The [GORC IM WG](#) outputs provide a firm foundation for the [GORC IG](#) as it seeks to create a roadmap for commons integration. They provide a firm, yet flexible, foundation for creating a set of recommendations and form the basis for working towards greater global interoperability. The long-term vision is to provide frictionless access to all research artefacts including, but not limited to: data, publications, software and compute resources; and metadata, vocabulary, and identification services with the appropriate protocols and support in place. This is the environment that will allow the research community to devote more time to research and less time to research infrastructure issues and associated overheads. It is an audacious goal and we believe that this model will advance our collective efforts in that direction.

4.2 Unpacking the name

The original GORC International Model has been applied in an increasing diversity of contexts since its release in 2023, and participants wanted to understand the model's intentions by revisiting the individual words in the title and the assumptions encoded therein.

4.2.1 Global

It was agreed that this term signifies the interoperability and federation of diverse commons around the globe, rather than a plan for creating a single, monolithic global entity. The Global Commons is essentially both distributed and virtual. The objective is to enable local and national commons to connect and interoperate at a global level, crossing national and disciplinary borders without assimilating their organisational and disciplinary structures.

4.2.2 Open

“Open” is often touted as a fundamental goal, but participants noted the global shift towards FAIR, which does not require absolute openness in order to

9. Payne, K., Corrie, B., Crawley, F., Harrower, N., Macneil, R., Maxwell, L., Sansone, S.-A., Treloar, A., Woodford, C., Åkerström, W. N., & RDA GORC International Model WG. (2023). *The Global Open Research Commons International Model Report, Version 1 (1.0)*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00097>

10. <https://www.unesco.org/en/open-science/about>

11. Ostrom, E. (1990). *Governing the commons: the evolution of institutions for collective action*. Cambridge University Press.

facilitate the reuse of research outputs. The agreed definition was grounded in the phrase “as open as possible, as restricted as necessary”. This implies both “responsibly open” and only “as restricted as necessary”, distinguishing it from absolute openness by allowing data to be shared within controlled, secured environments where this is necessary. The GORC International Model's purpose is to enable openness and interoperability within research data infrastructures, encompassing data, compute, software, and Virtual Research Environments (VREs). It is explicitly designed with values to promote equitable access and discourage profit-driven gatekeeping.

4.2.3 Research

In line with the *UNESCO Open Science Recommendation*¹⁰, “Science” was originally considered as an alternative to “Research” but in some English speaking countries the word Science explicitly does not include the Humanities, Arts and Social Sciences. Research broadly covers all kinds of investigation to ensure inclusivity and avoid disenfranchising any field of study. Importantly, it includes data **for** research, such as data from Galleries, Libraries, Archives, and Museums (GLAM) and government-collected data originally intended for internal administrative purposes, as well as the more conventional data **from** research.

4.2.4 Commons

Drawing on Elinor Ostrom's Nobel prize winning work on common pool resources¹¹, the GORC International Model posits that shared resources can be effectively governed, with a core value that profit is not the primary goal. A Commons is designed for communities that organise for their shared, mutual, or collective benefit. The GORC International Model adapts Ostrom's work to fit the context of encouraging global collaboration.

4.3 Use cases, needs and challenges

Several key issues arose and are discussed below. Recommendations for adopting the GORC International Model, and recommendations for changing it are summarised in chapters 4 and 5, and presented in more detail in the Appendices.

U1: [EGI](#) is using the model to think about its role in the context of the [European Open Science Cloud](#) (EOSC) Federation and to consider GORC governance and sustainability examples and best practices that are suitable for multi-supply federated environments.

U2: [SURF](#) is using the model as a reference model for engagement, planning and alignment when considering the services they provide and how these would appear as part of the Netherland's Large Scale Research Infrastructures (LSRI) and an EOSC National Node.

U3: [CSC](#) (Finland) and SURF (Netherlands) are adapting and utilising the GORC International Model in the context of developing national nodes for EOSC.

U4: The GORC International Model is a source of repository attributes for use in the RDA [Community-based catalogue of requirements for trustworthy Technical Repository Service Providers Working Group](#) (TRSPs) WG

U5: GORC is an organising Ontology for the [RDA Knowledge Base](#) (in development)

The following benefits appeared across more than one use case example:

Benefits of the GORC International Model	Use Case(s)
To serve as a common vocabulary, such as for EOSC, and for disparate organisations at national scale.	U1, U2, U3, U4, U5
To serve as a blueprint for data sharing and governance related to it.	U1
To provide a broader context for a specific objective - for example, sharing data requires additional provisions - AAI, monitoring, sustainability, etc.	U1, U3
To be potentially usable for commercial infrastructure providers - possibly with the exception of governance-related elements, and by generalising the current focus on research.	U1, U3
To be used by organisations to develop their own internal maturity models and measure progress, as well as set up their own benchmarking by describing what they do, how they do it and how it might be improved.	U1, U2, U3

It also became evident during the workshop that the GORC International Model is meeting a variety of needs, with potential for even more:

- **A need for a common organisational vocabulary:** A common vocabulary is important for organisations to facilitate their internal operations, and in order to interoperate either within federations or internationally. The GORC International Model establishes a common language that different initiatives can adopt to discuss interoperability at all levels: legal, semantic, technical, and organisational.
- **A need for interoperability to enable research workflows:** As in a complex digital research environment, digital objects, ICT infrastructure and services are offered by different stakeholders from different institutes and countries, it is fundamental that interoperability is in place among these to enable research workflows.
- **A need for interoperability of policies and processes:** In the case of a federated digital research infrastructure interoperability is necessary for federation members to operate supporting compatible access policies, support structures and human networks.
- **A need to illustrate best practices:** GORC illustrates how [FAIR](#) and [SAFE](#) best practices need to be complemented by additional technical and human elements – as well as community expectations such as [TRUST](#) and [CARE](#) – to realise the data and service value chain.
- **A need to accommodate future use cases** that do not follow a relatively open Commons participatory model, such as commercial cases and nuances around restricted data.
- **A need to describe the current state of research organizations** and to enable them to measure their progress in implementing their commons (without being prescriptive) via processes such as internal team-building exercises.

The workshop noted this diversity is both a strength and a weakness. It is a strength because it enables uptake in a variety of settings, but a weakness because optimising the GORC International Model for each use has the potential to fragment effort and slow progress. The consensus position of the workshop was that we should design for specific settings (and make those clear) but that we

could/would not stop use of the model outside those settings.

The discussion also identified a series of challenges in seeking to adopt the model.

Challenges	Use Case(s)
Features and attributes are sometimes linked to multiple essential elements or categories, and these links are context-dependent.	U1
The GORC International Model is missing blueprints for access policies, etc. across infrastructures.	U1
The GORC International Model might be used as a way of assessing commons maturity and benchmarking, although this was not the original intent.	U2
The GORC International Model is aimed at infrastructure providers, not researchers, but researchers are the beneficiaries. We need a point of engagement with the end users, and end-to-end workflows are one possibility.	U2
The GORC International Model represents a significant learning curve for newcomers.	U2
It is important to identify who is using the model, since this perspective changes how it is interpreted and applied.	U2
For infrastructure providers building a commons, the governance of the commons by multiple stakeholders as suggested by the GORC International Model may conflict with their existing governance structures/practices.	U3
It is important to continue to educate/train GORC's users as the model evolves.	U3

5. Outputs from the workshop

Over the course of the workshop it became clear that the participants wanted to make a series of recommendations for consideration by the GORC leadership group (this currently consists of the joint co-chairs of the GORC Interest and Working Groups). These recommendations fell into two groups:

- Recommendations for those wishing to adopt the GORC International Model (that is, primarily intended for those outside the GORC leadership), and
- Recommendations for improving the model (that is, primarily intended for those inside the GORC leadership)

This section of the report will present an overview of both sets of recommendations, with the detail to be found in the Appendices.

5.1 Recommendations for adopting the GORC International Model

It should be noted that while the original impetus for GORC was interoperability within and across commons, it has become clear that the GORC outputs may also be used for internal organisational needs, with or without interoperability in mind. By using the GORC outputs and adopting the GORC International Model, an organisation positions itself for international interoperability, even if that is not the current goal. Adoption of the GORC International Model and outputs also does not solve or directly provide solutions to the considerations provided, instead uncovering problems and questions for the organisation to address. The adoption recommendations are summarised below and further detail can be found in Appendix 2.

1. Identify your purpose for using the GORC International Model and the scope you wish to apply to the profile you create.
2. Determine the methodology for engaging with the model that best suits your organisation and purpose.
3. Connect your profile or use case example with your context and narrative.
4. Determine which essential element(s) you will prioritize to achieve impact.
5. Complete the profile for your current state and determine what you would like to do.

6. Provide feedback to the GORC initiative and consider allowing your profile, or parts of your profile, to be shared with other GORC users and community.

5.2 Recommendations for improvements to the GORC International Model initiative

Moving forward, the roles and responsibilities of the RDA GORC groups need to be clarified, the mission and value of the GORC initiative within and beyond RDA needs to be determined, and broader stakeholder engagement has to be planned and executed. Outlined below are the main recommendations that emerged from the workshop to improve the GORC initiative. Further detail can be found in Appendix 4.

1. Assess the aspiration, mission, value, and applicability of the GORC International Model.
2. The GORC International Model needs a more inclusive governance model, as well as links to the governance model in relevant GORC documents.
3. Create a registry of GORC International Model users for feedback and engagement.
4. Promote and facilitate GORC International Model adoption and use.
5. How Interoperability and Standards [& Conventions] are kept, represented, and incorporated into the typology diagram and the GORC International Model needs further work.
6. The content of Interoperability and Standards & Conventions in the GORC International Model should be revisited.
7. Create profile templates and tools for completing profiles.
8. Be flexible by allowing organisations to split or merge essential elements.
9. Create a planning tool based on the GORC International Model, providing levels of maturity for each item in the model.

12. Mappings here refer to conceptual mappings as well as more generic and unrestrained connections and pattern analysis between existing models, frameworks, and vocabularies with all or part of the GORC International Model. There is a Mapping task force within the GORC International Implementation Working Group focused on this area of work.

10. Create a collection mechanism for use cases and specific use case examples.
11. Identify stakeholders for each GORC essential element.
12. Create a portfolio of real-world use case examples, profiles, and adoption stories.
13. Identify good practices for sustainability, governance, and interoperability.
14. Create mappings¹² and slices of the GORC International Model that showcase which items facilitate specific principles, recommendations, policies, etc.
15. Refine the GORC International Model based on mappings and slices.
16. Create GORC profile templates for commons looking to become part of federations.
17. Develop good practices for adopting GORC by federated infrastructures.
18. The GORC International Model should be policy, principle, and recommendation agnostic, making it as simple as possible.
19. Improve the quality of the GORC International Model by adding metadata to the items in the model.
20. Improve the structure of the GORC International Model.

6. Next steps

For many of the attendees, they will both apply the GORC International model to their settings in ways that add value, and also contribute to ongoing development of the model through existing Task Groups and Task Forces that are underway under the auspices of the Research Data Alliance [GORC International Implementations Working Group](#). Here, the recommendations for adoption are probably the most relevant.

For the GORC leadership group, the recommendations for improvement provide an extensive work program that will no doubt take multiple years to deliver, and will require careful prioritisation as well as additional resourcing. Determining a plan for this is an obvious next step.

Making the Global Open Research Commons Truly Global

21 - 25 July 2025, Leiden, the Netherlands @lambda

Topics

- Presentation of adoption case studies
- Discussion of barriers to adoption
- Discussion of improvements to the model
- Work program for next 12 months

Scientific Organizers

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- CJ Woodford, Digital Research Alliance of Canada
- Laurents Sesink, SURF

The Lorentz Center organizes international workshops for researchers in all scientific disciplines. Its aim is to create an atmosphere that fosters collaborative work, discussions and interactions. For registration see: www.lorentzcenter.nl

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Appendix 1. Final Updated Workshop Program

Day/Purpose	Time	Activity
Monday:		
Settling in	09.30 - 10.00	Registration and coffee
Overview	10.00 - 10.30	Lorentz welcome, scene setting, overview of week, survey results, appoint rapporteurs for first day
Ensuring common ground	10.30 - 11.30	Overview of Essential Elements and International Model, GORC II WG and IG proposed work program
Getting to know	11.30 - 12.00	Organisation categorisation
Networking/trust building	12.00 - 13.15	Lunch and open discussion
GORC for a new commons	13.15 - 14.30	Case Study 1 and discussion - EGI
GORC for an existing commons	14.30 - 15.30	Case Study 2 and discussion - SURF
	15.30 - 16:00	Coffee
Review	16:00 - 16:15	Wrapup of day 1/plan for day 2
Review	16:15 - 16:45	Rapporteurs for day work on recap
Networking	17.00 - 18.00	Welcome Reception @Lambda
Networking	18.00 onwards	Dinner (own arrangements)

Day/Purpose	Time	Activity
Tuesday:		
Recap	09.00 - 09.30	Workshop rapporteurs for day 1 present their summary for discussion
What you wanted	09.30 - 09.45	Summary of responses to the registration questions
Unconferencing	09.45 - 10.15	Overview of process, and initial post-it work for possible topics
	10.15 - 10.45	Coffee
GORC for Commons Interoperability	10.45 - 11.45	Case Study 3 and discussion - EOSC
Unconferencing	11:45 - 12:00	Review and add to the post-it notes!
	12:00 - 13:15	Lunch and open discussion
GORC for RDA: vocabulary and mapping	13:15 - 13:45	Case study 4 (surprise!) and discussion - RDA work
Unconferencing	13:45 - 14:00	Review and add to the post-it notes! Organize post-its into topics/groups
Group work	14:00 - 15.15	Groups find somewhere to work and identify a rapporteur
	15.15 - 15:45	Coffee
Group work continues	15:45 - 16:30	Small group work sessions
Reviewing	16.30 - 17.00	Group rapporteurs for day work on recap
	17.00 onwards	Dinner (own arrangements)

Day/Purpose	Time	Activity
Wednesday:		
Report back and discussion	09.00 - 10.30	Group rapporteurs provide a report on what was discussed and actions arising Decision on topics for groups
	10.30 - 11.00	Coffee
	11.00 - 12.00	Continuation of Day 2 recap Uses of GORC (add to the board) Identification of topics for afternoon small group work sessions
	12.00 - 13.15	GROUP PHOTO Lunch and open discussion
	13.15 - 14.30	Small group work sessions
	14.30 - 15.00	Coffee
	15.00 - 16:15	Small group work sessions
	16.15 - 17.00	Group rapporteurs for day work on recap
	18.00 - 21.00	Offsite dinner - Lab 071
Thursday:		
Report back and discussion	09.00 - 10.30	Group rapporteurs provide a report on what was discussed and actions arising
	10.30 - 11.00	Coffee
	11.00 - 12.00	Continuation of recap from day 3, large group discussion
	12.00 - 13.15	Lunch and open discussion
	13.15 - 14:30	Small group work sessions
	14:30 - 15.00	Coffee
	15.00 - 16.15	Priority setting for future GORC work (Alt - 1. Small group work sessions 2. review your pre-workshop activity and complete your org. profile!)

Appendix 2. Recommendations for how to adopt the GORC International Model

Day/Purpose	Time	Activity
	16.15 - 17.00	Group rapporteurs for day work on recap
	20:15 - 21:30	Personal tour of the museum of antiquities - sign up!
Friday:		
Report back and discussion	09.00 - 10.30	Group rapporteurs provide a report on what was discussed and actions arising
	10.30 - 11.00	Coffee
Pulling it all together	11.00 - 12.00	<p>Wrapup, next steps, and thanks</p> <p>Activity: Review your pre-workshop activity and complete your org. Profile: How would you approach creating a profile for your organisation now vs what you did before the workshop? Who would you approach to help create the profile?</p> <p>What is 1+ things that you can or will do with the GORC International Model in the next 3-6 months?</p> <p>Regardless of what you do or how it goes, please let the organizers know! It will help inform how we proceed with communications, support, tooling, changes to the model, etc.</p> <p>How would this group like to be involved moving forward? Report from this workshop GORC initiative generally</p>
	12.00 - 13.30	Lunch and departure
	13.30 - ?	Co-ordinators meet to debrief

13. The GORC ecosystem is the network of GORC users, adopters, and developers who publish or present about their experience with the GORC outputs and/or participate in the GORC initiative

NOTE: The Improvement recommendations all start with "A", to distinguish them from the Improvement recommendations in Appendix 4.

A1. Identify your purpose for using the GORC International Model and the scope you wish to apply to the profile you create. This may be faceted, with primary and secondary benefits. Some possible use cases include:

- A. Supporting discussions / planning activities to position your organisation in the GORC ecosystem¹³
- B. "Presenting" your organisation as a commons (fitting it into a consistent structure) to increase external exposure and attract recognition as a commons
- C. Identifying relevant commons to learn from and define a trajectory to improve your commons in the GORC ecosystem
- D. Coordinating Commons' activities to share and align implementation within a country, domain, federation, etc.
- E. Internal activities such as planning governance, conducting self-assessment, or using the modelling process as a team-building exercise
- F. Creating a status report for your organisation via the model, and/or reporting to funders, stakeholders.

See [Appendix 3](#) for additional information on use cases A-D identified during the workshop.

Scope may change as you use the model and find new connections, however setting a boundary on what to consider in the modelling process early on is beneficial because the answers to the questions vary depending on the scope being considered. Some examples of scope include:

- Specific projects or programs
- Base services only
- One or a grouping of units in your organisation
- Your organisation on the whole, without considering external service providers or agreements
- Your organisation on the whole, including all existing external agreements and

mechanisms

- Your organisation as part of a larger federation, such as EOSC or LA Referencia

A2. Determine the methodology for engaging with the model that best suits your organisation and purpose.

Determine the GORC International Model stakeholder community, and the GORC International Model team (i.e. who will use the profile for their own needs and eventually complete all or portion of their organisation's GORC profile). Consider which tools you and the GORC team will use to navigate the model and at what granularity. For example, some users may only need to consider the GORC typology and not the model. You may also find that using a spreadsheet format works better for some while others work better with narrative tools for navigating the model. Experience to date has demonstrated the value of organizing GORC International Modelling as a team activity, engaging staff with different roles and points of view which should be reconciled during the modelling process.

A3. Connect your profile or use case example with your context and narrative.

This should be documented, addressing questions such as:

- Why did you decide to use the GORC International Model for the purpose you identified in A1.
- The mission and vision of your organisation.
- The main community or audience for your organisation, if not a consideration of all relevant stakeholders.
- Geographic, social, cultural, political, and economic context as appropriate.

For individual team members completing full or partial profiles, their roles and scope should be mentioned.

A4. Determine which essential element(s) you will prioritize to achieve impact,

especially if different ones are priorities for different people on the GORC team. This might involve each team member defining their core elements, drawing from the ones proposed in the model. Reasoning should be provided for this choice, and especially if essential elements are deliberately excluded. Note that in some situations it may be difficult to decide on priorities since many of the essential elements are linked.

A5. Complete the profile for your current state and determine what you would like to do.

You can use this as a baseline to compare against in future profiles to track improvement. If this is useful, organisations could set up

their own maturity model to both describe their current state using a shared vocabulary and to measure their progress in implementing GORC. Consider:

A5.1 Determining the role of each stakeholder group for each essential element. As each member of the GORC team evaluates the items in each essential element, they should consider how the stakeholders they interact with and know are impacted by the considerations in each essential element. Through the modelling process, this will indicate which considerations are relevant to each stakeholder group and how.

A5.2 GORC can be applied at different levels of granularity, to illustrate how parts of a digital infrastructure operate within one environment, how a distributed infrastructure is implemented integrating multiple parts in a multi-supplier environment, and how different digital infrastructure integrate at international level. You may consider only the essential elements, or specific item levels within the model such as essential elements, their categories, and related characteristics of both; or all items in the model, including subcategories and the most granular characteristics.

A5.3 GORC is intended to be principle-agnostic, however instantiations cannot be. Organisations should use the model to determine what is important and possible, using required and suggested community principles, standards, frameworks, and other policies to guide their implementation decisions.

A5.4 Provide rationale for why you might deviate from the model, including reorganisation, omission, and addition of items.

A6. Provide feedback to the GORC initiative and consider allowing your profile, or parts of your profile, to be shared with other GORC users and community. The [RDA GORC groups](#) are developing an open online space where profiles can be stored and shared.

Appendix 3. Proposed Use Cases of GORC adoption

Supporting discussions / planning activities to position your organisation' in the GORC ecosystem

Gains / reduced pains:

- Be perceived as a professional and informed participant in discussions around GORC and data commons more broadly, e.g. have a definitive answer to (how) we are (not) (contributing to) a commons
- Collecting internal views
- Identify differences of understanding/priorities across the organisation
- Find a shared understanding
- Identify gaps and set goals
- Creating consensus for a shared self-understanding/direction

Implementation concerns:

- Buy-in from management (could be a disruptive process but also very engaging)
- First pass through of the GORC to prioritise where to start and contextualise the model for use in the organisation

Stakeholders:

- Management group
- Key people from the organisation outside of the management group

“Presenting” your organisation as a commons (fitting it into the mold) to increase external exposure and getting recognition as a commons

Gains / reduced pains:

- Reaching new users
- Connecting with other commons
- Finding collaborators more broadly, e.g. on projects etc.
- Means of getting recognition / demonstrating impact

Implementation concerns:

- Your organisation might not see (or wish to see) itself as a commons
- Describing your organisation as a commons might not resonate with your external stakeholders

Stakeholders:

- Builders and operators
- End users
- Data providers
- Sponsors and funders

Identifying relevant commons to learn from and define a trajectory to improve your commons in the GORC ecosystem

Gains / reduced pains:

- Understanding the landscape
- Identify opportunities for improved interoperability
- Better development planning (less redundancy)
- Aligning the way you present different parts of your organisation to be able to compare and contrast with other using GORC as the shared frame of reference
- Learn from others how they have addressed features your are working on

Implementation concerns:

- Requires consistent use and sharing of the outputs of the GORC IM adoption tool, also a database / place to access these
- Information sharing might be sensitive, e.g. balancing confidential information related to competitive advantage

Stakeholders:

- Builders and operators
 - User engagement
 - Service development
 - Management
- Sponsors and funders

Coordinating Commons' activities to share and align implementation within a country, domain, federation, etc.

Gains / reduced pains:

- Strengthening collaboration
- Creating engagement and commitment
- Achieving alignment
- Interoperability

Implementation concerns:

- Including the right actors

Stakeholders:

- Builders and operators
- End users
- Data providers
- Sponsors and funders

Appendix 4. Recommendations for further development of the GORC International Model and associated outputs

NOTE: The Improvement recommendations all start with “I”, to distinguish them from the Adoption recommendations in Appendix 2.

Changes to the GORC Governance and Engagement

A developing theme over the course of the workshop was the question of how the future of the [GORC International Model](#) should be governed and by extension its engagement with users and adopters. This was raised in discussions about changes to the model, about sustainability of the model and ongoing maintenance of the model and associated outputs.

At present, the work on the Model is being undertaken within the [GORC International Implementations Working Group](#), and its associated Task Groups/Task Forces. But many of the attendees at the workshop clearly are invested in the success of the Model, yet are not involved in the Working Group.

The workshop revealed challenges in engaging diverse user communities and establishing sustainable governance structures. Participants considered whether the model should remain within RDA or transition to another organisation, and debated between open contribution models (where anyone can show up) versus intentional stakeholder engagement (where individuals/specific stakeholder representatives are intentionally invited).

The meeting concluded with recognition that the model serves those seeking to improve interoperability, but requires better governance frameworks and user feedback loops to remain relevant and useful over time. Infrastructure providers need to be hooked into the feedback process (but aren't now). Furthermore, the maintenance, improvements and creation of GORC outputs is currently dependent on a small number of individuals.

Specific recommendations include:

I1. Assess the aspiration, mission, value, and applicability of GORC.

Should the GORC outputs be specific to organisations based on a commons inspired governance and open by design, or should GORC outputs be more generic and applicable to all environments? It was noted that the GORC International Model is also applicable to research commons that are [FAIR](#)

but not Open (e.g. because they deal with sensitive data), and that the model could also be adopted by commercial providers that are not based on Commons governance. The GORC International Model is intended to be as simple as possible and principle-agnostic, making the potential user audience larger than the originally intended audience. Consider:

I1.1 Identify the current guiding principles of the GORC, the RDA GORC groups, and the GORC initiative. For the RDA GORC groups and the wider GORC initiative, determine if their missions are the same, and if not how they are connected. Distinguishing and making more clear the separation between the GORC typology and the GORC International Model may be necessary.

I1.2 Determine how the original RDA GORC group motivations have changed and map onto the current group motivations. Identify how the original understanding of “GORC” influenced the methodology and creation of the model, and make that clear in communications. For determining the current mission and value, consideration should be given to if commons need to have shared values, what the value is for the commons themselves, researchers and other end users, and how the existing and intended future GORC outputs serve the GORC mission and the needs of GORC stakeholders.

I2. GORC needs a more inclusive governance model, links to the governance model in relevant GORC documents (so it is clear to people who are considering adoption), **and a viable long-term home.** Starting with a [RACI](#) chart (who is Responsible, Accountable, Consulted, Informed) for GORC and identifying who is responsible, accountable, should be consulted and informed about the initiative, its outputs, and changes to those outputs will potentially identify what sort of governance structure is best suited for GORC now and in the near future. The governance of GORC must reflect the mission and value of the GORC initiative.

I3. Create a registry of GORC users for feedback and engagement.

Beyond the RDA GORC group posting and discussion options, a registry of users allows transparency in who is interested in GORC and creating outputs using GORC as well as facilitating communication with users and gathering feedback on suggested changes and published outputs. Having better engagement with users may lead to the identification of GORC best practices, such as for national research infrastructures and data services,

as well as unintentional discipline focus, such as an overrepresentation of natural science research commons.

14. Promote GORC adoption and use. In addition to creating more robust feedback mechanisms with users, additional engagement mechanisms should be used for promoting GORC and communicating its value. This may include (1) creating infographics and visual aids to explain use and adoption options as well as the content of the GORC International Model, and (2) choosing a well-known and open platform to host and navigate GORC outputs, such as GitHub.

15. Facilitating GORC adoption and use. Various avenues can be considered such as:

Selected GORC organisational profiles compiled with descriptive narrative and further promoted

Training and/or workshops with examples of how to use the model and curating those examples

Examples for funders, indicating the value of all elements for interoperability

Specifically target [EOSC](#) alignment, by mapping and linking EOSC guidelines and rules of participation to GORC

Explore the applicability of the GORC International Model to other federations which could use the model as a tool for their own alignment and publish their findings

Improvements to the GORC outputs

The materials available for review and use by the workshop participants were those already published by the RDA GORC groups or otherwise made available, including the [GORC Typology](#), the [GORC International Model](#), the [Model Narrative Report](#), and the [GORC International Model V1.1 adoption tool](#). The co-organizers later drafted and shared a [narrative version of the adoption tool](#) based on participant feedback.

There are several GORC outputs being created and drafted by the current RDA GORC II WG, including:

GORC profiles of existing organisations and documentation needed for model use and adoption (Task Group 1 + 3)

A GORC profile template for national data services (GORC/NDS Task Force, in collaboration with the [RDA National Data Services IG](#))

Mappings between the GORC International Model and other models, frameworks, and vocabularies that are in use by the research commons community and the semantic backend work required to facilitate these mappings (Task Group 2 + 5)

Determining the connection and relationship between the GORC International Model and the MaLDReTH model (GORC+MaLDReTH Task Force, in collaboration with the [Mapping the Landscape of Digital Research Tools/MaLDReTH II WG](#))

Thematic slices of the model, to identify connections between items and essential elements for particular roles, stakeholders, and concepts such as FAIR or research data management (Task Group 4)

Many of the recommendations in this chapter align with the planned work of the GORC II WG, and reinforce the goals of each TG and TF. How the recommendations here impact the work of each TG / TF as well as potentially new or other groups that can work on GORC outputs is discussed further in the following chapter.

The role of Interoperability

The original Typology of Essential Elements had Interoperability and Standards as the central hexagon. This blended two different concerns: the desire to work towards increased interoperability, and the importance of standards in facilitating interoperability. A subsequent revision removed Interoperability from the diagram, leaving the central hexagon as just Standards. This change did not remove Interoperability from the model, however – it is retained in a separate tab. A planned future change (prior to

the workshop) was to change Standards to Standards and Conventions to reflect the importance of *de facto* and *de jure* standards.

The workshop discussed the question of interoperability on a number of occasions, and with different combinations of attendees in the small groups. Each time, recommendations were brought back to the larger group for ratification (or not). Arguments were expressed for both removing and keeping interoperability from the essential elements, and from the diagram, but the group did not come to consensus.

The conclusion was:

16. How Interoperability and Standards [& Conventions] are kept, represented, and incorporated into the typology diagram and the model needs further work. This might involve expanding the essential elements to include more hexagons and keeping both in the model, integrating one or the other into other essential elements and keeping a central element, or some other option.

17. The content of Interoperability and Standards & Conventions in the model should be revisited. The definition of standards needs to consider Standards used by and made by an organisation (that are not official standards). Interoperability needs to consider aspects such as interoperability within and between commons, mapping with the [European interoperability framework](#), semantic and conceptual modelling aspects beyond technology, and if there are situations where interoperability should be avoided.

Profiles, use cases, and the tools to create them

Profiles were a major discussion topic for the workshop, considering what they should include, who should complete them, and how they would be gathered, represented, and navigated. Profiles are specific instantiations of the GORC International Model for a particular organisation or scope set by a user, say for a collection of organisations or for a particular project within an organisation. There was also interest in the development of profile templates, where commons with similar interests or contexts could focus on a subset of GORC considerations.

Emergent from the discussions on profiles was the need for use cases of the GORC International Model, which could be used by organisations to justify the creation of a profile or use of the model otherwise. Use cases describe the benefits, gains, implementations, and relevant stakeholders for a particular use of the model, which can be used by adopters to create business cases for GORC adoption. Use case examples are the specific subsets or additions to a use case for their particular context. A set of draft use cases was developed during the workshop, and can be found in [the Appendix](#).

Recommendations regarding profiles and use cases include:

18. Create profile templates and tools for completing profiles. There are several high priority profile templates that should be created and shared with the community in the short term, namely for national data services and for [EOSC nodes](#). Tools for creating profiles should be formalized and made available, including narrative tools that include context questions and approach suggestions. Consideration is needed for if users should be able to customize the typology in their profile creation, which dimensions to determine for each item in the profile, and how to capture organisations changing over time within and across profiles. Dimensions suggested during the workshop included urgency, cost, importance, effort, value, risks, status/implementation stage, and maturity.

Additionally:

18.1 Be flexible by allowing organisations to split or merge essential elements. This approach would allow GORC to be adopted by different initiatives according to their organisational needs.

18.2 Create a planning tool based on the model, providing levels of maturity for each item in the model. This planning tool would result in a profile of an organisation, with additional information on maturity and intent.

19. Create a collection mechanism for use cases and specific use case examples. Value narratives will be particularly helpful in collecting use cases, and preventing GORC outputs from misuse. Care should be taken to avoid GORC being used as a checklist or certification, and instead as a practical tool that can be used in many ways.

I10 Identify stakeholders for each essential GORC element (e.g. funders, users, service providers, infrastructure operators, content providers etc.). When doing so, refer to existing information models defining these stakeholders. Consider if some are more important and why, for which elements, in which use cases, and what the approaches could be per stakeholder group. Some possible approaches include (1) User journey/ persona development for target GORC users, (2) Recommendations to funders for building/sustaining research commons, (3) User guide per stakeholder group, including examples, slide decks, etc., such as for Chief Financial Officers, and (4) how different groups can come together to create a commons (guidebook for workshop facilitation, e.g. infra service provider, research object provider, etc.).

I11. Create a portfolio of real-world use case examples, profiles, and adoption stories. A collection of reflections and specific uses of the GORC International Model that can be shared and used to develop future GORC outputs, including refinements to the model, and to promote adoption and use of the GORC outputs. This portfolio could be hosted or facilitated by the [RDA annotator](#) (when available), the [Data Stewardship Wizard](#), [GitHub](#), or an independent web interface. Consideration for time-stamping and versioning profiles to capture that organisations change over time, as well as organisation and navigation of the portfolio such as through tags are needed.

I12. Identify good practices for sustainability, governance, and interoperability. These would be beneficial to align existing governance and funding to the 'Commons' model which is expected to be participatory. Identifying good practices will arise from gathering examples of governance and sustainability in practice, as well as practical examples of interoperability such as through user stories of workflows across commons. Sustainability examples should not shy away from discussing different income sources and costs. The combination of these practical examples with use case examples and profiles will highlight what makes a "good" research commons.

Mappings, slices, and connections between parts of the model

"Mappings" here refer to conceptual mappings as well as more generic and unrestrained connection and pattern analysis between models, frameworks, vocabularies, and all or part of the GORC International Model. The goal of mappings is to identify where the GORC International Model complements existing models in use and where it may fill gaps or provide a bridge to further considerations. Slices are thematic subsets of the model that cut across essential elements, connecting items relevant to a particular role or topic such as academic librarians or FAIR.

There were several recommendations for models and frameworks to map with the GORC International Model, and it was decided quickly that while a list could be generated at the workshop, it was not a useful exercise during the workshop to start a mapping where there is already a task group in the GORC II WG focused on this work. The list of mapping suggestions was passed promptly back to this task group for prioritizing their work in the short term. Higher level recommendations for mappings and slices include:

I13. GORC and other interoperability frameworks. It is important to [map](#) GORC to similar models and relevant vocabularies where terms may be different. GORC can also be aligned with established information models, for example by considering actors and concepts defined in [DCAT](#), [schema.org](#), the European interoperability framework, vocabularies of data infrastructure terms, and others.

I14. Create mappings and slices of the model that showcase which items facilitate specific principles, recommendations, policies, etc. Priority examples include FAIR, [CARE](#), [TRUST](#), [CTS](#), EOSC interoperability framework, and [POSI](#). Aligning the essential elements with the stages of project management, slices for different kinds of interoperability and for interoperability of specific items such as Authorization and Authentication Infrastructure (AAI), and determining if and when parts of the model should be and remain disconnected from each other are also of key interest. Investigation of a minimum viable commons slice, which would define when an initiative or organisation becomes a research commons, would provide a

guideline for those interested in developing commons from the ground up and is a high value output.

I15. Refine the model based on mappings and slices. Revise the model content to include potentially useful relevant refinements, including new items as well as examples. Consider refinements to the model structure as appropriate. It is noted that in addition to refinements suggested from mappings and slices, another source of refinements is the ongoing literature analysis in GORC II WG, in addition to the proposed feedback loop for profiles suggested in the previous section.

Federations of commons

A federation of commons is defined here as an organisation connecting two or more commons to the same end-user community and providing shared resources across the connected commons. A federation of commons may not be a commons itself. Examples include EOSC and [LA Referencia](#).

Much of the discussion around how the GORC outputs would support federations of commons and commons looking to participate in federations divided into topics of profiles, stakeholder mappings, slices, and connections between the essential elements. A key need is practical examples of how different models of federations operate, which would be facilitated by the creation and use of GORC profile templates for commons looking to join these federations. Therefore:

I16. Create GORC profile templates for commons looking to become part of federations, in particular an EOSC node profile template. Considerations for interoperability in a federated system, when and how to hand over responsibility and control of services to another node or a central hub and which items in the GORC International Model could be handed over, as well as governance frictions are required.

I17. Develop good practices for adopting GORC by federated infrastructures. Identify small changes to the GORC elements or model that could make it a better fit in the effort to federate infrastructures (e.g.

we do not have seamless authentication for data infrastructures). This may be created as a slice of the GORC International Model.

Changes to the model

Significant discussion in both small and large groups occurred on changes to the model. Ultimately, it was agreed that any changes to the model items and their structure should only be implemented once feedback is received from users and adopters (i.e. examples can be added without issue). However, it is anticipated that some changes will be beneficial to improve use of the model and should be considered as part of the next version release of the model:

I18. The model should be policy, principle, and recommendation agnostic, making it as simple as possible. Organisational context can then be applied to the model while creating a profile, which reflects the organisation's choices in their context. This may require rewording, removing, or adding items to the model. In particular, "consideration level" should be removed, as it is better used in profile tools and templates instead of the model itself. However, there are implicit principles in the model based on international interoperability, and so the model should be made more explicit about these connections and touchpoints.

I19. Improve the quality of the model by adding metadata to the items in the model. Each item in the model should be reviewed to make explicit which recommendations, frameworks, policies, and other community documentation promote or suggest the implementation of that item; is phrased such that it can be measurable over time; and is agnostic to implementation.

I20. Improve the knowledge organisation, or structure, of the model. Revisit the current conceptual model and its application in each essential element for consistency. Connections between related essential elements should be made more apparent in any restructuring, and could include pointers from one essential element to another if an item could belong to or is related to both. For example, the relationship between human capacity and services & tools, where all services require internal capacity to function,

documentation for users, and so on. Some specific considerations include:

I20.1 Integrate sustainability more fully into other elements, which may reduce the total number of items.

I20.2 Consider splitting ICT Infrastructure and Services & Tools into “enabling hardware and services” and “research-facing services”. It was agreed in the workshop that connecting GORC and the MaLDReTH model would be beneficial for users, and making such a distinction in services may facilitate integrating the models. A comprehensive analysis of enabling vs research-facing services may be needed to avoid gaps. This work will be further discussed by the MaLDReTH/GORC task force.

I20.3 The model glossary needs to be made more prominent and integrated into the GORC outputs. This may be facilitated by creating a GORC semantic object, reorganizing the model, or interlinking the glossary more fully.

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